

Comparative analysis of articles written in the analytical genre in the press of Uzbekistan and abroad

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Abstract: The style of writing an article in the analytical genre differs depending on which country and for which people it is being written. For example, Western and American audiences are receptive to material consisting of only facts, and consider it biased to refer to the journalist's additional opinion and conclusion. The Russian audience cannot accept the material without emotion and evaluation, and considers it imperfect. Not only the audience, but also Russian theorists argue that journalistic investigation of a dry investigative article should be different from law enforcement investigation.

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Differs depending on which country and for which people it is being written. For example, the Western and American audience accepts the material consisting of only facts, and considers it biased to refer to the additional opinion and conclusion of the journalist. And the Russian audience cannot accept the material without emotion and evaluation, and considers it imperfect. Not only the audience, but also Russian theorists argue that journalistic investigation of a dry investigative article should be different from law enforcement investigation. Based on this, it is justified for a Russian journalist to analyze the facts and assess the situation. Everyone knows the difference between the printed editions of Uzbekistan and European countries. In some sense, it is closely related to the values and customs of nations. In the West, views such as modesty and hypocrisy have existed for a long time, and this, in turn, has caused us to lag behind Western countries in the field of journalism.

The ability to clearly state one's opinion, to justify it, to consider events and events from different perspectives is an important component of analytical skills, which can be used in preparing articles for various media channels, publishing video material, preparing social advertisements on important issues, or discussing debates. can be used in the organization. Freedom of expression should not be allowed to be restricted. In order to study the issue objectively and present its results regardless of what they are, it is necessary to fully open the space of creativity to the journalist. Only then, journalism will develop and this, in turn, will serve the development of the state ¹.

In the 90s of the 20th century, journalistic investigations required by the theory of journalism were "Khalk sozi", "Hurriyat", "Mohiyat", "Huquq", "Voice of Uzbekistan", "Trust", "XXI Asr", "Pravda Vostoka", "ZerkaloXXI". , began appearing in "Novosti Uzbekistana", "Adolat", "Inson va Kanon" newspapers. They mainly highlighted the shortcomings of socio-economic reforms. Also, violations of human rights and freedoms, violations of the law in the activities of the court and prosecutor's office were discussed.

Journalistic psychology of the Lomonosov Moscow State University, answered the question of "Can a journalist lie in necessary situations in his work?" asked by students at an online conference, "No, it should never be allowed. "But you can change your profession," he answered. But in the modern mass media, the use of false information and methods of obtaining information has increased in order to gain false popularity. The soon-to-be-popular Wikileaks website, specialized in disclosing classified information, made a big splash around the world. The site began to publish secret correspondence of American diplomats. Before that, he disclosed many secret documents related to Iraq and Afghanistan. About 90,000 official documents containing hitherto

¹Imnazarov K.T., Mamatova Ya.M. Information and printing (Introductory course lecture). - T.: NUUz, 2000. - S. 6.

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undisclosed details of the war in Afghanistan have been released to public attention on the website. The document published in the British "Guardian", American "New York Times" and German "Spiegel" publications at the same time as "Wikileaks" is called "Afghan War Diary". These are secret documents covering the war in Afghanistan, and someone secretly delivered them to Wikileaks. The WikiLeaks group has made it a practice to disclose information secretly supplied by sources among the military, security forces, government agencies and businessmen. Many countries, especially the United States, consider this an attack and a threat to the country's national security. The documents were suspected to have been provided by one of the American military analysts, and the analyst was brought to court. The founder of the site, Julian Assange, was arrested, but after some time, he was released on a large bail. A number of American companies serving the web page stopped cooperation with "Wikileaks". Internet domain companies in America stopped serving Wikileaks, resulting in the site moving its address to a Swiss domain. US senators have called on all companies and organizations that provide services to the website to cut ties with them.

American print media is considered a "cold" language. Sometimes you can find insulting words in it. The article expresses opinions not only against the virus, but also against the country's president and his policies. So, is the journalist right? Of course, only a journalist who knows politics and economy can work with such crude analyses. That is why writing analytical articles in America is divided into a separate section. Only journalists with special expertise will be able to write articles in analytical genres.

Most of the analytical articles in America are focused on the topic of corruption. The growth of interest in this direction of journalistic activity by both journalists and the mass media audience is explained by the fact that journalism is viewed as one of the powerful means of social control over the activities of state institutions, as an effective means of fighting against the arbitrariness of officials and the expansion of corruption.

"However, these tasks are standard methods of journalism it is not always possible to do it using. It is not written on his forehead that the official is corrupt and bribe-taking. His press secretary does not have such words in his vocabulary. It is for this reason that journalists who are able to independently find information began to appear in newspaper editorial offices and on television, and the materials they write began to be submitted under the column "Journalist inquiry"³. The opinion of many experts working in the field of journalism in the USA regarding the journalistic inquiry goes back to the fact that this phenomenon is characteristic only of the press of developed, democratic countries, where freedom of speech and diversity of opinions are widely allowed. However, this does not mean that this line of research is impossible in the conditions of a developing democracy. It is in such countries that it is necessary to learn and develop the best traditions and style of democratic journalism. This becomes a guarantee of the success of fundamental changes and reforms carried out by the state. Journalistic inquiry is considered as one of the indicators of the state of democracy in the society and a means of building a strong civil society and achieving the principle of balance between all branches of government. Analytical journalism has already taken a leading position in advanced Western countries. Such journalism is interested in the fact that the mass media audience knows the truth about the hidden aspects of important events, events, and processes. "Only the information obtained as a result of careful and careful analysis can reveal the true essence of the event, explain the actions of people related to it, and also show the reader that journalists really serve the interests of people and that they are representatives of "people's power"⁴.

² www.bbcuzbek.com

³ Journalistic research: Istoriya metoda i sovremennaya praktika./ Pod obshch. ed. A.D. Konstantinova. – SPb.: ID "Neva", 2001. – C.12.

⁴ Nesterenko F.P., Irnazarov K.T., Mamatova Ya.M. Working journalist: professionalism, creativity, mastery. Flying pos. Chast1. - T.: Zar Kalam, 2002. - C. 135.